

Research

Noise-Induced Hearing Loss (NIHL) Among Miners: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis

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Abstract

The mining industry plays a major role in the world's economy, however; it is considered one of the most dangerous sectors. The sector is also known as a hub for many occupational health and safety (OHS) diseases, notable among these diseases is noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL). The study's main objective is to unveil the major causes of NIHL among miners and how to curb this problem by drawing inferences from secondary data. In this systematic review and meta-analysis, data was gathered from PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar with the following keywords: noise-induced hearing loss, hearing impairment, occupational noise, and mining industry. PRISMA and STROBE were used for screening, eligibility, and inclusion of the studies. This review combined narrative synthesis and quantitative analysis using the comprehensive meta-analysis (CMA) software. The review included 19 studies with 47,734 miners; the highest hearing impairment prevalence was 75.2% (95% CI 72.5-77.7). Due to this high prevalence, the main causes of NIHL were identified as age, gender, exposure duration, and the type of occupation. Miners working around the processing plant were seen to be at higher risk than others in other working areas. Additionally, lack of education and training, late detection of illness, mining environment, and unwillingness to use hearing protection devices (HPDs) were also seen as additional causes. This requires proper structures that will encourage workers to wear hearing protection devices (HPDs) and systems that will aid early detection of NIHL among miners.

Keywords: NIHL; OHS; Hearing threshold; Mining

Introduction

The industrial sector is faced with diverse occupational health and safety (OHS) issues. These health issues range from respiratory, musculoskeletal, psychological, and dermal to auditory [1] among others. As a result of the prevalence of these health issues in the industrial sectors, especially in the mining environment, there is a need to carefully study these problems and propose specific solutions to them. Among many sectors under the industrial sector, the mining industry was selected because it plays an essential role in the world's economy by serving as one of the major sources that produce almost all the raw materials patronized in most sectors in the world [2]. Even though this sector provides the world with so much value, it also remains one of the most dangerous workplaces based on the number of people exposed to risk [3]. Occupational accidents and diseases have considerable immediate effects as well as prolonged social and economic repercussions on communities and governments. Medical expenses, compensation disbursements, production delays, and legal costs exemplify direct expenditures. Over time, expenditures such as lost output, accident investigations,

remedial training, diminished morale, and increased absenteeism accumulate [4].

The mining industry is complex and multidisciplinary, operating under highly dynamic conditions. Control measures must be implemented for various released gases, generated dust, and noises related to blasting or rock crashing. Additionally, attention must be given to numerous ergonomic postures, heavy machinery, vehicles, conveyors, and especially noise exposure [3]. As a result of these hazards, miners face various risks, which may result in work-related diseases, injuries, disabilities, or fatalities. Mining accidents represent a complex interplay of multiple risk factors. Noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) is among the common work-related diseases that are associated with miners.

Noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) refers to sensorineural deafness resulting from prolonged noise exposure [5]. The World Health Organization (2017) estimates that around 360 million individuals globally experience severe hearing loss, while approximately 1.1 billion young people (ages 12 to 35) are at risk of hearing loss due to noise exposure [6]. These global statistics indicate the severity of this health problem to individuals, not only in the mining environment. This disease places much emphasis on the level of sound that an individual is exposed to. The epidemiology of noise reveals that if an individual is exposed to noise above 85 dB for a longer time, it can lead to NIHL. However, it is interesting to note that in addition to loud noise, various other risk factors, both modifiable and non-modifiable, can contribute to the progression of noise-induced hearing loss. Risk factors can be categorized into modifiable factors such as smoking, diabetes, and lack of exercise, and non-modifiable factors including aging, race, and genetics. These factors may intersect with noise and expedite the onset of noise-induced hearing loss [5].

In the United States, more than 30 million workers are subjected to hazardous noise levels (85 dB and above), as measured by A-weighted noise exposure normalized to an 8-hour workday [7]. Additionally, between 7.4 and 10 million industrial workers face the risk of hearing loss due to occupational noise exposure [8]. According to ElahiShirvan et al. (2020) [9], noise-induced hearing loss typically manifests within the initial 10-15 years of employment for individuals exposed to high-frequency sounds (exceeding 4000 Hz). Audiometry is a technique used to evaluate individuals' hearing sensitivity, thereby elucidating the characteristics, severity, and potential origins of hearing impairment [10]. This technique involves presenting auditory stimuli at varying intensity levels to the individual and the responses are subsequently recorded. The hearing threshold is defined by the minimum intensity level of stimulus that elicits a consistent response from the individual. The results of this diagnostic test, referred to as an audiogram, can inform the selection of suitable treatments and hearing aids [9].

Prior primary studies on NIHL have presented findings that focused on unique aspects such as audiometric findings, case-control studies, and cross-sectional studies to reveal the reality of this health issue. In this systematic review and meta-analysis, we aim to present the prevalence of NIHL in the mining sector, the advancement in preventive measures, and suggest ways that this health concern can be curtailed in the mining industry.

Materials and Methods

The initial search was conducted in October 2023. Related studies were identified through searches in PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar using the terms ("Noise-Induced Hearing Loss" OR "Hearing impairment" OR "Occupational hearing loss") AND ("Coal miners" OR "Mining industry" OR "mining environment" OR mining). To ensure a comprehensive search, no restrictions were placed on the language or year of publication of the articles, and the identified information was imported into the EndNote reference management software. The duplicated references were removed from Endnote and the final articles were exported to Rayyan for screening and inclusion of references. To maximize the number of relevant studies, the reference lists of the identified related articles were manually reviewed. The most recent updates to the searches occurred in December 2023, indicating that the reviewed studies were assessed without restrictions from the inception of the study until that date. A manual search of the reviewed articles was also undertaken to access all desired articles and prevent the deletion of related ones. All the authors did the screening and the selection process to ensure that the relevant data for the current study were included.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The criteria for study inclusion were as follows: 1) Research indicating the prevalence of hearing impairments in mining workers, 2) primary studies, including cross-sectional, cohort designs and case studies, 3) articles in English 4) Studies for which the full text was available, 5) Studies with sufficient data (sample size, prevalence percentage) which had at least 16 elements of the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) checklist, and 6) studies that focused on NIHL and discussed either the causes, preventions, and risk factors.

The criteria considered for the exclusion of studies included: 1) Reviews, reports, conference papers, and books. 2) Duplicates; 3) Studies with insufficient data (sample size, prevalence percentage), 4) studies in other languages other than English, and Studies which discussed NIHL in its general context in addition to other OHS diseases.

Study Selection and Data Extraction

This systematic review and meta-analysis adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. Following the initial phase of PRISMA, specifically study identification, duplicates

identified across various searched databases were excluded. The initial selection and assessment of papers were performed based on their titles and abstracts, leading to the removal of irrelevant articles by the defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The complete texts of the papers were evaluated based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Similarly, studies that were not relevant were excluded. We emailed the authors of publications as needed to obtain additional information. To mitigate bias, each phase of source evaluation and data extraction was performed independently by two reviewers. In cases of disagreement between the two reviewers, a third reviewer assessed the paper. The data from all selected studies were subsequently collected using a pre-established checklist. The checklist includes the first author's name, publication year, research location, sample size, prevalence, number of individuals with hearing impairments, average age, and sector.

Quality Assessment

A checklist suitable for observational studies was utilized to assess the quality of articles. The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) checklist comprises six components: title, abstract, introduction, methods, results, and discussion. This checklist comprises 32 sub-scales (items). The 32 items represent different methodological components of the study, including the title, problem statement, study objectives, study type, study population, sampling method, sampling strategy, definitions of variables and procedures, data collection tools, statistical analysis methods, and findings. Articles with scores of 16 and above were classified as having medium to high methodological quality and were included in the analysis. Articles with scores below 16 were classified as low quality and subsequently excluded from the study. A total of 1,394 references were identified from the data search. Of these, 462 duplicates were detected by Endnote. A screening of 932 references based on titles and abstracts resulted in the exclusion of 655 references. Out of 45 articles sorted for retrieval, only 40 were successfully retrieved. Nineteen articles [7, 9, 11-27] were included in the study according to the established inclusion criteria as illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Results and Discussions

From **Table 1**, it is evident that the majority of the studies were cross-sectional, with only four being cohort studies. This study encompasses a variety of mining industries, including gold, coal, silver, quarry, and bauxite, ensuring a comprehensive exploration of the sector. The age and duration of exposure emerged as the central theme across all studies and were identified as the key factors contributing to a miner's susceptibility to NIHL. The study was categorized by continent, highlighting the prevalence of NIHL as shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2 depicts the analysis drawn from a total of thirteen studies that reported the prevalence rate of NIHL. The rate or the occurrence of NIHL serves as the effect size index. The analysis utilized a random-effects model. The studies included in the analysis are considered to represent a random sample from a broader pool of potential studies, and this analysis aims to draw inferences applicable to the sample [28]. The average effect size is 0.335, accompanied by a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.199 to 0.505. The average effect size across similar studies may lie within this range. The Q-statistic serves to posit that every study included in the analysis exhibits a uniform effect size. If every study had the same true effect size, the anticipated value of Q would match the degrees of freedom, which is the total number of studies minus one. The Q-value stands at 1422.999, accompanied by 12 degrees of freedom and a p-value of less than 0.001. With a criterion alpha set at 0.100, we can dismiss the null hypothesis suggesting that the true effect size remains consistent across all these studies. The I-squared statistic stands at 99%, indicating that approximately 99% of the variance in observed effects is attributable to variance in true effects, rather than being a result of sampling error. Assuming that the actual effects follow a normal distribution, we can estimate the prediction interval to be between 0.026 and 0.906. The actual effect size for 95% of all similar populations is contained within this range [29, 30]. The meta-analysis of the study was further conducted using the odds ratio (OR) and confidence interval as shown in **Figure 2**.

The analysis in Figure 2 is based on the studies included in this review. The index of effect size is represented by the odds ratio. The analysis utilized a random-effects model. The studies included in the analysis are considered a random sample from a broader universe of potential studies, and this analysis aims to draw inferences about that universe [30]. The average effect size is 7.778, accompanied by a 95% confidence interval ranging from 4.444 to 13.614. The average effect size across similar studies may lie within this range. The Z-value evaluates the null hypothesis asserting that the mean effect size equals 1.000. The Z-value stands at 7.183, indicating a p-value of less than 0.001. With a criterion alpha set at 0.050, we dismiss the null hypothesis and determine that among populations similar to those examined, the mean effect size is not exactly 1.000.

Fig. 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram for Study Selection

Authors, year	Study location	Mine type	Study design	Sample	Age	Noise Exposure levels	Exposure duration	Prevalence/incidence of NIHL (%)	Predictors of NIHL
(Amedofu, 2002)[11]	Ghana	Gold	Cross-sectional	252	<20 - >50	>85dba	-	235	Noise levels and noise exposure
(ChadambukaMususa and Muteti, 2013)[12]	Zimbabwe	-	Cross-sectional	169	19-49>	>85dba	-	37.2	Noise level, age, duration of exposure
(ElahiShirvan et al., 2020)[9]	Iran	-	Cross-sectional	150	20-35, 36-50, and >50	>85dba	Long term	-	Age, work experience, equivalent sound

(Erol, 2022)[13]	Turkey	Coal	Cross-sectional	399	20-60	>90db	1-25years	31.5	level, and frequency
(Gyamfi et al., 2016)[14]	Ghana	Quarry	Cross-sectional	400	<20 - >58	87.5db	-	25	Occupational group, age, duration of exposure
(Hessel and Sluis-Cremer, 1987)[15]	South Africa	-	Cohort	2667	20- >40	85-105db	5-30 years	-	Gender, age, and duration of exposure
(Ishtiaq et al., 2014)[16]	Pakistan	Coal mine	Cross-sectional	400	<20, 20-25, 26-30, 31-35, and >36	-	-	29	The current occupation, the number of years at that occupation, and the use of hearing protection on the job.
(KanjiKhoza-Shangase and Ntlhakana, 2019)[17]	South Africa	Gold and non-ferrous	Cross-sectional	90	20- >60	-	>10years	38.9	Unhygienic occupational environment and noise
(Kesici et al., 2016)[18]	Turkey	Silver mine	Cross-sectional	373	18-53	-	>15 years	Related to arsenic exposure	Age, gender, race, education, years of experience
(Liebenberg et al., 2023)[19]	Australia	Coal	Cross-sectional	72	20- >60	-	-	59.7	Age, smoking, working time, and blood arsenic exposure
(Liu et al., 2016)[20]	China	Coal	Cross-sectional	738	43	>85	>10years	20%	Age, duration of exposure, and main sections
									Age, sex, BMI, length of service, education level,

(Madsen et al., 1998)[21]	USA	Coal	Cohort	102	31-92	-	Long term	58.8	smoking, alcohol consumption, and family history of CVD. Mine size, mine experience of workers, and mine location, that is, above or below ground.
(Moroe, 2020)[22]	South Africa	-	Cross-sectional	16	-	-	-	High awareness of NIHL	Duration, levels of compensation payout, educational level
(Naicker, 2024)[23]	South Africa	Coal	Cross-sectional	241	20-60	>6 high	>10years	-	Age, gender, education, job specification, and duration
(Nikulin et al., 2021)[24]	Ukraine	Coal	Cross-sectional	15	23-55	>85	Long term	High prevalence	Noise level, occupations, age
(Strauss et al., 2014)[25]	South Africa	Gold	Cohort	40123	16-65	-	>10years	Correlation with age-related loss	Age, gender, and race
(Tripathy and Rao, 2017)[26]	India	Bauxite	Cross-sectional	247	28-63	90-100	>5 years	34.4	Noise levels, occupation
(Ullman et al., 2021)[7]	USA	Quarry	Cross-sectional	200	18 to 67	-	-	26.5	Frequency of perceived high noise exposure and number of years worked in a high noise environment.

(ViljoenNie and UK Guest, 2006)[27]	Coal	Cohort	1080	<29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-59,	-	-	75.2	Age and noise
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Table 1: Descriptive Summary of Included Studies

Continent	Countries	NHIL Frequency	Sample	NIHL prevalence rate	Logit event rate	Std Err
Africa	Ghana	59	252	0.234	-1.185	0.149
	Zimbabwe	63	169	0.373	-0.520	0.159
	Ghana	100	400	0.25	-1.099	0.115
	South Africa	165	2667	6.19	-2.719	8.045
	South Africa	35	90	0.389	-0.452	0.216
Europe	Turkey	126	399	0.316	-0.773	0.107
	Australia	43	72	0.597	0.394	0.260
	UK	812	1080	0.752	1.108	7.046
Asia	Pakistan	116	400	0.290	-0.895	0.110
	China	148	738	0.201	-1.383	9.192
	India	84	247	0.340	-0.663	0.134
North America	USA	60	102	0.589	0.357	0.201
	USA	53	200	0.265	-1.020	0.160

Table 2: Prevalence of NIHL Among Miners

Noise Induced Hearing Loss Among Miners

Fig 2: Forest plot for age and hearing impairments among miners

The Q-statistic serves as a means to evaluate the null hypothesis, which posits that all studies included in the analysis exhibit a uniform effect size. If every study reflected the same true effect size, the anticipated value of Q would correspond to the degrees of freedom, which is calculated as the number of studies minus one. The Q-value stands at 2772.220, accompanied by 18 degrees of freedom and a p-value of less than 0.001. With a criterion alpha set at 0.100, we can dismiss the null hypothesis suggesting that the true effect size remains consistent across all these studies. The I-squared statistic stands at 99%, indicating that approximately 99% of the variance in observed effects is attributable to variance in true effects, rather than to sampling error. Assuming that the true effects follow a normal distribution, we can estimate the prediction interval to be between 0.559 and 108.218. The actual effect size for 95% of all similar populations is contained within this range. Analyses were performed utilizing Comprehensive Meta-Analysis Version 4 [28]. The meta-regression was also conducted using the mean duration of exposure as the moderator variable and this is shown in Figure 3.

Fig 1: Meta-regression study of the mean duration of noise exposure by miners

Demographic Characteristics and NIHL

A significant predictor we identified was the demographic characteristics of workers. The demographics encompassed age, duration of exposure, and occupation type. This section examined the relationship between these factors and NIHL, highlighting their significance. ElahiShirvan et al. (2020)[9] indicated that there is a significant relationship between occupation, industrial noise levels, and duration of exposure in the development of NIHL among miners. Additionally, these studies also proved that there is a direct relationship between NIHL and the duration of exposure [13, 14]. For instance, in the US, over 30 million workers are exposed to dangerous noises (85db and above) and as a result 7.4-10 million industrial workers are at risk of hearing loss caused by occupational noise [9]. Exposure of employees to noise in terms of years was found in the range of 4 to 37 years [26]. Employees with longer tenures in the mining sector are more likely to develop NIHL due to cumulative exposure. Noise-induced hearing loss commonly occurs in the first 10-15 years of work if workers are in contact with high-frequency noises (over 4000 Hz) [9]. The longer the duration of noise exposure, the higher the prevalence of NIHL. Based on the results by Tripathy and Rao (2017) [26], it can be argued that the risk of hearing loss is higher for those working in the production groups. Boring machines, electro-hydraulic drills or jumbos, jackhammers, electro-hydraulic loaders, and pick hammers have been used for many years during

underground development and production works in coal mines, the difference that exists between the hearing thresholds among workers from various working environments indicates the influence of the working environment on the hearing threshold of miners [13].

Exposure to extremely noisy environments for 8 hours per day work is associated with injuries/accidents [16]. This is because all the machines used at the various quarries produced noise that exceeded the minimum threshold with levels ranging from 85.5 dBA to 102.7 [24]. The severity of hearing impairment increases the relative risk of single and multiple events when threshold levels exceed 15dB of hearing loss [19]. Ishtiaq et al. (2014)[16] found a relatively high prevalence rate of 37% among coal miners with ear problems and the major complaint was hearing loss; while hearing impairment was extremely high and an even higher percentage of hearing deficit was reported after 55 years. Other reported ear problems are within 5 years and predominantly hearing loss was the most frequent ear problem; while in another study it was observed as 31% among coal miners and interestingly the prevalence of ear disorders increased significantly with their duration of exposure to the unhygienic occupational environment and high noise [13]. Age and hearing loss were identified as variables that may be factors in the occurrence of accidents. Median threshold values for all frequencies progressively become more elevated as participants in the noise-exposed group become older [26]. Therefore, the most pretentious employees tend to be in the 40-60 age range, as the cumulative effects of noise exposure become more apparent with age [22]. NIHL tend to increase as a function of age regardless in younger mine workers although less common, may also experience NIHL if exposed to high levels of noise early in their careers, especially if proper hearing protection is not used [31-33]. However, it is noteworthy that almost all age groups are at risk of having hearing loss. In addition, those who have been exposed to noise for 10-14 years are 3.5 times more likely to have hearing loss when compared to those who were exposed to noise for 15 years or more [34, 35]. The reason for this surprising claim is that the miners, with 10-14 years of exposure, have not yet adapted to the mining environment which causes great damage to their hearing, however workers over 15 years have already experienced hearing loss and thus, their susceptibility is less. The working environment or the type of work was also seen to impact the risk of NIHL. The difference in hearing thresholds among miners from various working environments was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating the influence of the working environment on the hearing threshold of the workers [17, 23]. Miners who are highly affected are mostly found around places that generate higher noise thresholds. Excessive noise levels are mostly prevalent in plant processing, underground mining, and underground workshops [12]. Although the sound pressure levels experienced by blasters are high, they are exposed for only a few seconds, whereas the operators are exposed continuously for 8 hours to 90-110db and are more prone to experiencing NIHL [36, 37]. Administrative staff and supervisors who work in areas distant from production environments, although less exposed to high noise levels may still suffer from secondary exposure [38, 39]. Miners with NIHL get 'acclimatized' to their positions and can carry out their duties without risk to safety arising [40]. If that is the case, these workers may be using sensory cues that are not reliant on hearing. Miners could be exposed to a mixture of high and low-frequency background noise for extended periods. Such noise could be loud enough to damage the unprotected hearing mechanism. Research indicates that excessive exposure to high-frequency industrial noise that causes damage to the hearing mechanism results in hearing loss of the high frequencies [4, 41]. Such hearing loss may also be associated with cardiovascular, social, and psychological health problems [27]. Thus, the age of a miner, the workstation (in the mine), and the duration of noise exposure are the key susceptible indicators to hearing loss. The most dangerous place in the mine was found to be the processing plant area.

Major causes of hearing loss

In Michigan alone, around 86,000 people are suffering from noise-induced hearing loss [7]. This statistic is not only for the miners but all the people in the city. This makes it imperative to assess the causes of hearing loss, especially among coal miners and the results can be translated to other fields. In 1990, \$200 million was paid in compensation for hearing loss caused by noise exposure [21]. On the other hand, over the past 10 years, the proportion of the European population at risk of exposure to noises above 65 dB has increased from 15% to 26% [9, 19, 42]. Noise is creating dangerously alarming situations in all industries and causing problems due to work-related factors that include occupational noise, whole body vibration, work-related diseases, and toxic exposures. Age, duration of exposure, and sound level for an 8-hour Time Weighted Average are also shown to have a strong relation with ear disorders among coal miners as discussed earlier [16]. However, these are not all the causes that there is to hearing loss among miners.

Lack of proper training of coal miners was identified to be one of the main causes of occupational injuries, especially ear problems [2, 16]. Most miners lack proper inductions and reminders causing mine dangers, mine culture, and mine PPE relevance to last but a few, these improve the sustainability of mine employees while improving the safety culture of mines. Mine management does not have hearing conservation programs to protect employees against hazardous noise, they lack administrative controls and do not adhere to permissible exposure limits according to the noise regulations. NIHL is due to a lack of noise prevention programs and awareness of the consequences of excessive noise exposure [5,

43]. Education of mineworkers on hearing conservation is one of the challenges contributing to the setback in achieving NIHL elimination targets [17]. KanjiKhoza-Shangase and Ntlhakana (2019)[17] found that the use of protective equipment is not treated as a priority training area. Moreover, NIHL awareness training also lacks tailor-made contextually responsive training to meet the educational and linguistic needs of the mineworkers. We suggest that all employees should be properly trained and when under supervision, are properly supervised by a competent person, provided with personal protective equipment and clothing where necessary, and that these are used. This will help safeguard the employees against dangerous machinery, hazardous processes, noise, and dust and provide them with a safe and healthy work environment.

In addition to the lack of training, the studies also indicated that another major cause of hearing loss among miners is the unwillingness to use protective equipment. The inconsistent use of hearing protection devices (HPDs) is also an important finding as it shows poor transference of knowledge into practice in the early stages of employment [17]. The behavior of the miners as well as their attitude were essential factors for the usage of hearing protection devices. Coal miners are known to work in areas near noise, increasing their risk of hearing impairment in the future. Most underground work involves machinery that produces noise like; cutters, drills, transporting, loading, and unloading [16]. The miners did not generally use hearing protectors based on the findings of most of the studies. Only 13.2% in 1979 and 17.2% in 1982 reported the use of hearing protection and many of these used hearing protection part of the time [21]. While the increase in the use of hearing protection during the 3 years is encouraging, even the higher level of use is likely to be inadequate given the pervasiveness of noise in the industry. In other circumstances, HPDs were not available at many of the mines, or the miners were not aware of their availability [44, 45]. In addition, fewer than 1 in 4 stated that they had received information or training about the dangers of noise but the use of personal protective devices is difficult ground because of the heat and humidity [32, 46]. This requires the production of protective devices that are conducive to underground.

Another interesting finding from these studies was that, there is a general concern that while miners are using hearing protection devices they might hear important alerts which is dangerous to their safety. Erol (2022)[13] argued that the use of personal protective devices must also be essential part of comprehensive hearing conservation programs. Including other reasons why miners do not feel comfortable wearing HPDs is that communication because difficult with other works. Communicating in the mining industry is important, thus, not hearing other workers were described as uncomfortable to miners. Other reasons include the belief that HPD causes ear infections and that they are unsure how to obtain a good fit or seal when using HPDs [23]. Thus, the reasons why miners decide not to wear HPDs might be associated with their personal beliefs and perceptions.

According to this analysis, the underreporting of occupational diseases is caused by several variables, including the lengthy latency time between exposure and start, the generic character of signs and symptoms, and the difficulty in linking a particular workplace exposure to an illness. Miners are susceptible to recurrent or cumulative trauma disorders and noise-induced hearing loss. The development of impairments is a potential outcome of an accident or disease, but the Mine Safety and Health Administration (MSHA) does not record rates of hearing impairment, arthritis, and chronic issues brought on by injuries annually, in contrast to miner fatalities and acute injuries [47-49].

Additionally, as automation has increased, coal production rates have risen steadily, while the labor force involved in coal mining has steadily declined [50]. Miners now face additional risks as a result of a greater dependence on large gear. In worker surveys, occupational diseases are often underreported. The primary sources of total noise exposure profiles are thought to include continuously operating equipment, iron and ore crushers, compressors, power tools, air tools, air conditioning, and exhaust fans [51]. Vehicles and transportation, which were divided into the following categories: heavy mobile equipment, light vehicles, reverse alarms, and airplanes, were thought to be the second greatest source of noise [52]. The perceived noise exposure profile also included specific operations like blasting, welding, or steel cutting, which were followed by loudspeakers, radios, or music [53].

In their study, Chadambuka et. al. (2013)[12] stated that the mean hearing loss of male workers at 4 kHz was higher than it was for female workers. Despite the same working conditions hearing loss can differ among different individuals. Hearing losses that start after the age of 40 years, and which, gradually increase and spread, generally draw attention and certain chemical [20]. The lack of systematic tracking of chronic health problems is one of the major causes of hearing loss [35]. Some mining organizations fail to track ear issues before they become disorders. Early diagnosis gives room to attack the problem before it becomes severe. Ishii et al. (2018) [54] clinical research suggests that melanin, especially in the stria vascularize of the cochlea, appears to act as a protective agent. According to the study's findings, black individuals in the subterranean noise group had significantly higher hearing thresholds than white participants, regardless of gender, for medians and 95th percentiles. Compared to white males, black individuals can tolerate higher noise levels better. Black individuals exposed to noise have been shown to have higher hearing thresholds than their white counterparts since 1931 [25]. Hearing is a sensitive structure, therefore it seems sense that arsenic would harm it.

It is well known that arsenic poisoning results in polyneuritis in sensitive structures. Although there is little information on how arsenic exposure affects hearing from earlier research, it has been noted that arsenic may damage hearing in urine and that quantities of the acid were substantially linked to hearing impairments [18]. It can be said that arsenic is one heavy metal that leads to hearing disorders.

The intensity has a significant impact on noise-induced hearing loss. The hearing organ is not significantly harmed by a noise intensity of 80 dBA. According to several studies, hearing loss occurs at noise levels between 85 and 90 dBA [7, 11, 19, 24]. In a study conducted in the USA, it was stated that the rate of occupational hearing loss was 67% in 197 people who were exposed to 89 dBA noise and the frequency of the noise [7]. Comparatively, it was stated that high-frequency sounds mainly result in effects such as high blood pressure, fatigue, and hearing loss [40]. The status that causes a downward tendency in the thresholds of 4 000 Hz and 6 000 Hz in the audio duration of exposure metric curve and shows an upward tendency again at 8 000 Hz is a symptom of noise-induced hearing loss [13]. Noise-induced hearing losses usually emerge at frequencies of 3 000–6 000 Hz, with the greatest loss being seen at 4 000 Hz, duration of exposure; the World Health Organization (WHO) stated that in those workplaces with a noise level of 85 dBA, 1% of those individuals who had worked there for 5 years, 3% of those who had worked there for 10 years, and 5% of those who had worked there for 15 years would experience noise-induced hearing loss [13, 26].

Recommendations for Curbing NIHL

This review offers very valuable information regarding demographic data and occupationally induced noise that may lead to hearing loss (NIHL). The systematic approach to reviewing the literature on this topic allows for a better understanding of how multiple factors interact to contribute to workers' hearing loss, especially in high-velocity industries such as mining and other high-noise exposure scenarios. There are some areas where this could have been done better and would have enhanced the impact. The conversation points to major gaps in noise prevention programs, hearing conservation programs, and training of workers. This can be achieved by employing structured preventive measures including formalized hearing conservation programs in addition to compliance with allowable exposure limits [55]. Further, organizations should invest in and use noise-reducing machinery and PPE to suit the more extreme conditions of mining environments [56]. Such measures would provide a strong framework for protecting workers' hearing in high-risk industries.

Education and training are critical components of any strategy to reduce the impact of noise in the workplace [57, 58]. Workers need to better understand the dangers of occupational noise exposure and how to use hearing protection devices (HPDs) appropriately. Thus, to achieve better compliance these training modules must be customized for different groups of people i.e. for the workers concerning their culture and their language. An understanding of these needs can enhance engagement and develop a better safety culture in an organization. We also acknowledged that HPDs use would also be hindered by behavioural and psychological factors including discomfort, communication barriers, and low perceived risk. These challenges can be best met by making protective clothing more comfortable and developing programs to change corporate culture and reward incentive schemes [59, 60]. This will help ensure that workers perceive HPDs as important safety tools and then consistent usage will increase, particularly in high-exposure scenarios.

Additionally, we suggest that occupational health strategies such as routine hearing tests and regular monitoring of hearing health are imperative. This will help identify hearing loss early help curb its deterioration and lessen physical and financial health impacts as well [61]. It is essential for organizations to also implement routine health audits and utilize advanced audiometric testing to keep track of hearing thresholds. Implementing systems for regular monitoring of auditory health would facilitate timely interventions and improve results. In addition to monitoring, it is important to enhance occupational safety policies in the mining environment. Regular monitoring of auditory health would allow for early intervention to optimize outcomes. Along with monitoring, the mining environment should improve the occupational safety policy [62]. Enforcing policies on existing noise limits and requiring personal protective equipment in hazardous environments are important steps. Employers are also responsible for keeping working conditions safe, management should also be accountable to employees in terms of observing prescribed noise limit levels. More importantly, integrating noise control measures into broader OHS policy will create a more comprehensive strategy for addressing NIHL. The article examines variations in susceptibility to hearing loss by age, gender, and ethnicity. Widening this focus and addressing disparities in workplace protections and outcomes could deepen the conversation. Such an intersectional approach would shed light on how occupational noise affects different worker demographics and guide targeted interventions to address their specific vulnerabilities [62]. It is essential to give greater consideration to environmental and technological factors. Further exploration is needed regarding the impact of contaminants like arsenic on auditory health issues, as well as the development of strategies to mitigate these risks. Furthermore, encouraging the advancement and implementation of quieter technologies in processing facilities, workshops, and other high-risk environments would contribute to a decrease in overall noise exposure. NIHL also has broader health implications and

is associated with cardiovascular and psychological disorders, resulting in a need to combat the risks from noise across the work environment [21]. Highlighting these broader effects is critical to building the case for comprehensive prevention and intervention strategies that target more than just auditory health.

Ultimately, we could raise the profile of global and sector-specific awareness campaigns about the importance of preventing occupational hearing loss. The focus is on mining, but the results can apply to many other high-noise environments. The article can also spread best practices and takeaways around occupational noise management, as it applies learnings from mining across industries. By incorporating these recommendations, the work would connect research findings with practical applications, serving as a valuable resource for occupational health professionals, policymakers, and industry stakeholders. This would deepen the comprehension of NIHL and motivate practical measures to protect the health and well-being of the miners.

Conclusion

Noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) is seen to be a pressing occupational health and safety issue, especially in the mining environment. Amidst the advancement of technology to curb this issue, the opposite keeps on occurring. The prevalence of hearing loss keeps surging which makes it concerning to employers and policy makers. Age, gender, level of noise exposure, and the duration of exposure have been the major risk predictors of hearing loss in addition to lack of training, and unwillingness to use HPDs by workers among many other factors were discovered to be the causes. Thus, there is a pressing need for employee training, especially on the important use of HPDs. NIHL reduction in miners will help prevent cardiovascular and psychological occupational illnesses. Tackling these issues will see the sector lessen the extensive impact of workplace noise and the overall well-being of employees.

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